

2-Methyl-benzimidazole (III): Hot PPA (12ml; 20g) was added to a reaction mass of the diamine (5.4g) and the β -ketoester (7.0ml) containing a drop of concentrated hydrochloric acid. Turbid layer, separated during reaction, disappeared on stirring. The reaction mass was stirred at 120-130° for 2½ hours. It was treated with ice and just neutralised; the product (3.2g.) was crystallised from hot water; m. p. 175°; its mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen of 2-methyl-benzimidazole was undepressed.

Acetoacet-o-aminoanilide (IV): *o*-Phenylenediamine (5.4g) was added to a solution of orthophosphoric acid (12 ml) containing β -ketoester (6.8 ml), externally cooled with ice; phosphorous pentoxide (20g) was added to this solution in small lots; the mixture was then heated on steam-bath for ½ hour. The reaction mass was treated with ice and neutralised with ammonium and sodium hydroxide giving yellow product. Yellow needles from aqueous ethanol (2.68g; m.p. 105° dec).

Analysis: $C_{10}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 14.58%
 found N, 14.50%

It coupled with diazotised amines giving deep red colour; its benzene solution on boiling gave benzimidazole-2-acetone (m.p. 118°).

References

1. W. A. SEXTON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 303.
2. O. HINSBERG and P. KOLLER, *Ber.*, 1896, 29, 1500.
3. G. W. WHELAND, *Advanced Organic Chemistry*, John Wiley and Sons, p 408.
3. R. S. MORRELL and A. E. BELLARS, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1904, 85, 345 and 1520.
4. F. UHLIG and H. R. SNYDER; *Advances in Organic Chemistry-Methods and Results*; 1960, I, 35. Interscience publishers, Inc. New York.

Acid Catalysed Isomerisation of 3-Epi-Moretenyl Acetate

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3-EPI-MORETENYL acetate¹ (I) on acid isomerisation under mild condition of Fazakerley and co-workers² (AcOH-H₂SO₄) furnished hop-17(21)-en-3 α -yl acetate (II), m. p. 222-23°, [α]_D + 11.1°. The acetate (II) on

hydrolysis (Methanolic-KOH) gave the corresponding alcohol-hop-17(21)-en-3 α -ol^{3,4} (III), m. p. 185-86°, [α]_D + 47° which on oxidation with CrO₃-Py complex yielded hopenone-I (identified by m. m. p and IR comparison with an authentic sample prepared from moretenone¹). The alcohol (III) was also prepared from hopenone-I by Meerwein-Pondorff reduction⁵ and was found to be identical (m. m. p. and IR).

Hop-17(21)-en-3-yl acetate on further isomerisation under strong acid condition of Fazakerley and co-workers² (AcOH-C₆H₅-H₂SO₄) yielded an acetate, hop-13(18)-en-3 α -yl acetate, (IV), m. p. 179-81°, [α]_D -32 1°, which on hydrolysis (Methanolic-KOH) furnished the alcohol, hop-13(18)-en-3 α -ol, (V), m. p. 219-21°, [α]_D 14.8°. Oxidation (CrO₃-Py) of the alcohol (V) furnished a ketone, m. p. 148-50°, [α]_D 49°, identical with hopenone-II (m. m. p). Meerwein-Pondorff reduction⁵ of Hopenone-II yielded an alcohol which was found to be identical with the alcohol (V) and its acetate with (IV) (m.m.p)

References

1. H. N. KHASTGIR, B. P. PRADHAN, A. M. DUFFIELD and L. J. DURHAM, *Chem. Comm.*, 1967, 1217.
2. H. FAZAKERLEY, T. G. HALSALL, and E. R. H. JONES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1877.
3. H. R. ARTHUR, S. W. TAM and V. AUGSUSING, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1960, 506.
4. WAI-HAAN HUI and MAN-MOON LI, *Phytochemistry*, 1976, 15, 427.
5. A. C. PATON, F. S. SPRING and R. STEVENSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2640.